

ANALYSIS OF COAL EXPLOITATION TRENDS

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Abstract: *The mining industry plays a key role in the planetary economy, from exploration to the exploitation of mineral resources, ensuring the production of electricity necessary for modern life. In addition, it employs a large number of people. Since the beginning of industrialization in the 19th century, coal has had a significant impact on the world's energy supply. Despite widespread calls for a shift to clean energy sources, to this day, coal represents the second largest primary energy source in the world. Issues of using renewable energy sources represent essential not only existential but also political views on the way and quality of life, as well as the fate of future generations.*

Keywords: *Coal, electricity, power plant.*

1. MINING INDUSTRY

Many mining companies produce a diverse range of minerals to minimize exposure to volatile and unpredictable market prices. They are known as diversified mining companies. Although many of the world's largest mining companies are based in the United Kingdom, mainland Europe or Australia, in recent years many Chinese mining companies have become increasingly prominent and have increasing revenues. BHP (Australia), Rio Tinto (UK/Australia), China Shenhua Energy (China), Glencore (Switzerland), Vale (Brazil), Anglo American (UK), Teck Resources (Canada), Saudi Arabian Mining Company (Ma'aden) (Saudi Arabia) are among the largest mining companies, which normally operate in several countries.

Figure 1. Global share of mine production volume in 2022 by region (M.Garside et al., 2024a)

2. COAL EMISSIONS AROUND THE WORLD

The burning of fossil fuels is the primary cause of rising global temperatures, and no fuel has contributed more to this than coal. Coal is the primary source of energy used as a means of producing electricity and heat. It was one of the first fuels used in the energy sector with a major contribution to the industrial revolution. Today, coal is still the world's largest source of electricity production. Despite being the dirtiest and most polluting fossil fuel, coal remains the largest source of electricity generation worldwide. In fact, coal-fired electricity was responsible for 21% of total global greenhouse gas emissions in 2021, making it the largest climate polluter. As the world aims to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, the transition from coal to clean energy sources will be a key area of focus for all governments in the future (Ian Tiseo, 2024).

3. GLOBAL COAL MINING INDUSTRY

Renewable energy production has been steadily increasing over the past decades, with solar and wind energy showing the greatest growth. However, the contribution of renewables to the world's electricity mix remains small compared to fossil fuels.

In the last three decades, coal has been the main source of electricity generation in the world. The total production of energy from coal in 2023 was almost 10,500 terawatt-hours. Overall, coal, natural gas and other fossil fuels accounted for about 60% of total electricity production. Fossil fuels remain the largest source of electricity generation worldwide. In 2023, coal accounted for roughly 35.5% of the global electricity mix, followed by natural gas at 23%.

Figure 2. Electricity production. of energy by energy consumption in the world (1990 - 2023, in terawatt-hours) (Statista Research Departmen, 2024a)

To meet demand, the global mining industry has increased annual production since 2000 and has maintained it at a nearly constant level. However, it should also be noted that coal has by far the largest reserves of all non-renewable energy sources. In 2022, hard coal accounted for 45.8% of the world's proven non-renewable energy reserves. Meanwhile, conventional oil accounted for about 18% of reserves.

Figure 3. Overview of global non-renewable energy reserves in 2022 according to sources (Statista Research Department, 2024b)

At current electricity production rates, coal and lignite reserves are sufficient for more than a hundred years. Unlike oil and gas, coal is widely distributed throughout the world. The largest concentration of reserves is represented in the USA, Russia and China.

Figure 4. Global coal and lignite reserves, December 31, 2021 (Eurocoal)

Primary energy production in the Republic of Serbia is based mainly on the use of coal. It can also be stated that there has been a noticeable decline in the use of coal in recent years.

Table 1. Electricity production in the Republic of Serbia from 2017 to 2021, by energy sources (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia)

Energy	2017		2018		2019		2020		2021	
	TJ	%								
Coal	302.127	68.23	276.720	65.37	285.772	66.22	295.064	65.11	263.034	61.58
Hydroelectric power	35.107	7.93	41.015	9.69	36.714	8.51	32.524	7.16	40.624	9.51
Solar photovoltaic energy	47	0.01	47	0.01	49	0.01	48	0.01	49	0.01
Wind energy	175	0.04	542	0.13	3,234	0.75	3,512	0.77	3,904	0.91
Crude oil and natural gas liquids	40.914	9.24	40.310	9.52	38,990	9.03	38,030	8.38	36,967	8.65
Firewood, wood chips and the rest	45.395	10.25	46,931	11.08	49,151	11.39	67,334	14.83	66,938	15.67
Natural gas	18.117	4.09	16,653	3.93	16,247	3.76	15,133	3.33	13,414	3.14
Geothermal energy	222	0.05	219	0.05	220	0.05	212	0.05	63	0.01
Biogas	723	0.16	939	0.22	1,190	0.28	1,624	0.36	2,221	0.52

Over the past half century, the world's electricity consumption has grown continuously, reaching approximately 27,000 terawatt-hours by 2023. Between 1980 and 2023, electricity consumption more than tripled, while the global population reached 8 billion people. The growth of industrialization and access to electricity further increased the demand for electricity. For example, China's GDP has grown by an incredible 15 times since 2000, making it the world's second largest economy, behind the United States. To fuel its industrial development, China needs more energy than any other country. As a result, it has become the largest consumer of electricity in the world and requires more than 8,000 terawatt-hours.

Figure 5. Electricity consumption in the world in 2023 by leading country (in terawatt-hours) (Statista Research Department, 2024c)

However, the per capita electricity consumption of the world's largest population is almost ten times less than that of Iceland, even though the energy used in this country came almost entirely from clean sources. Iceland is by far the largest consumer of electricity per capita in the world. On average, it consumes 53.9 megawatt-hours per person in 2023. This is the result of a combination of factors, such as cheap electricity generation, increased demand for heating and the presence of energy-intensive industries in the country.

Figure 6. Electricity consumption per capita in 2023 (Statista Research Department, 2024d)

China has the largest number of coal-fired power plants in the world. As of July 2024, there were 1,161 operational coal-fired power plants on the Chinese mainland, four times the number of such plants in second-place India, for example. Over 50% of the total global electricity production from coal is realized in China.

Figure 7. Countries with the largest number of coal-fired power plants in the world as of July 2024 (Statista Research Department, 2024e)

The capacities of the Republic of Serbia for the production of electricity managed by EPS have a total capacity of 7,855 MW. Eight thermal power plants with 25 coal-fired units, with a total capacity of 5,171 MW, produce about 70 percent of the electricity in the Republic of Serbia, while about 30 percent is obtained from 16 hydroelectric plants. The average coal production at mines in EPS ranges from 37 to 40 million tons of coal (EPS). In 2022, Indonesia exported about 471 million metric tons of coal, making it the world's largest coal exporting country. Australia is in second place, with coal exports of 359 million metric tons that year.

Figure 8. Leading coal exporting countries in 2022 (M. Garside, 2024b)

4. CONCLUSION

The structure of primary energy production is largely determined by the natural resources of a territory, but also by its strategic political decisions that affect the development of specific energy sources, such as renewable energy sources. Following the increased efforts of governments to fight against global warming, the share of renewable sources in the production of electricity has experienced a more pronounced growth in recent years compared to the use of fossil fuels. Projections show that renewable energy sources will surpass fossil fuels as the main source of energy by 2040. The key message of the work is the fact that the use of renewable energy sources is far below the expected result to which the countries of the energy community have committed themselves. The lack of results is not only a consequence of the lack of investor interest, but the presence of various influencing factors. Economic, political, social are only some of the most significant, which stand in the way of the construction of most projects of renewable energy sources. In this sense, it is

necessary to define achievable goals and guidelines for the improvement of renewable energy policy at the most intensive level.

LITERATURE

- Garside, M. (2024a, December). *Global share of mine production volume 2022, by region*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1474291/global-mine-production-volume-distribution-by-region/>
- Tiseo, I. (2024a, July). *Coal emissions worldwide – statistics & facts*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/topics/10428/coal-emissions-worldwide/#topicOverview>
- Statista Research Department. (2024b, October). *Global electricity generation 1990–2023, by source*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/273273/world-electricity-generation-by-energy-source/>
- Statista Research Department. (2024, May). *Global non-renewable energy reserves breakdown 2022, by source*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/263230/proportion-of-non-renewable-energy-reserves/>
- Euracoal. (n.d.). *Coal use worldwide*. <https://euracoal.eu/coal/coal-use-worldwide/>
- Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia. (2020–2024). *Statistical calendar of the Republic of Serbia*. Belgrade: SORS.
- Statista Research Department. (2024c, October). *Global electricity consumption 2023, by country*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/267081/electricity-consumption-in-selected-countries-worldwide/>
- Statista Research Department. (2024d, August). *Per capita electricity consumption worldwide 2023, by selected country*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/383633/worldwide-consumption-of-electricity-by-country/>
- Statista Research Department. (2024e, September). *Global operational coal-fired power stations by country 2024*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/859266/number-of-coal-power-plants-by-country/>
- Elektroprivreda Srbije (EPS). (n.d.). *Official website*. <https://www.eps.rs>
- Garside, M. (2024b, August). *Global leading coal exporting countries 2022*. Statista. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/270952/global-hard-coal-exports-2009/>